

Importance of Training to Organizational Performance: A case study of Fauji Fertilizer ...

Importance of Training to Organizational Performance: A case study of Fauji Fertilizer Company Limited

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Abstract

This paper investigates the importance of training to organizational performance, based on a case study of Fauji Fertilizer Company Limited (FFC). A sample of 7 respondents were interviewed from different levels of management. The findings of the study suggest that training programs have a large impact on organizational performance in FFC. Most respondents believed that training conducted by FFC has helped in improving the overall performance of the organization in terms of increased productivity, quality, profits and customer satisfaction. Moreover, the findings revealed that employees are more motivated and engaged when companies provide appropriate and effective training. Additionally, it was found that senior managers consider training as an important factor in the organization's success as it decreases employee turnover and enhances team morale. The results showed that the investment in training in FFC has an overall positive effect on organizational performance and that investment in training should be further encouraged in order to ensure a healthy and productive workforce.

Keywords: Training, Organizational Performance, Fauji Fertilizer Company Limited

Introduction

Employee training is an important practice of developing the knowledge and skills of employees so they can perform their roles more effectively (Arslan, Z et al, 2012). It

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encompasses a variety of activities and methods, including classroom instruction, on-the-job training, simulation, and e-learning (Gillani, A. 2021). Employee training has been a focused area of management research since the early 1900s. During this time, researchers have found employee training to be an effective tool for increasing organizational performance and employee satisfaction. For example, research has shown that employee training can enhance job knowledge, job skills, work motivation, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction (Mian, S. N. 2010). Training also helps employees develop better job-related attitudes and skills, which can lead to greater turnover and reduced absenteeism (Gillani, A. 2021).

Employee training is the process of developing the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of employees towards improved job performance (Khalid, W., & Khan, S. 2017). Training enables workers to perform, be more productive, increase job security, and ultimately, increase organizational effectiveness and performance (Kibria A. et al, 2022). Employee training has been highlighted in the literature as a key factor in organizational performance, as it improves the overall abilities of employees and positively affects outcomes and productivity. According to Ahmed, A., et al, (2017) employee training increases worker commitment to organizational goals, enhances knowledge and skills related to job performance, and encourages better work habits. This, in turn, increases worker productivity, profitability, and organizational performances. In addition, Kibria A et al, (2021) attributes improved organizational performance to the increased employee proficiency that comes with effective employee training. Employee training focuses on providing employees with new skills and knowledge so that they can perform their jobs more efficiently, adding value to the organization (Khalid, W., & Khan, S. 2017). Thus, organizations with entire staffs that have received appropriate training are more competitive, have higher job satisfaction, and achieve better overall performance. Moreover, Ahmed, A., et al, (2017) found strong evidence that, through training, organizations increase the job satisfaction of their employees, which leads to greater motivation to work hard and positively contribute to the organization's overall performance. It has also been shown that by investing in employee training, organizations have improved customer satisfaction, thereby increasing their revenues (Awan, A. G., & Saeed, S. 2015). Clearly, employee training is an effective strategy for achieving organizational performance. In summary, employee training can significantly contribute to improved organizational performance, and is thus an important strategy for organizations to pursue. By providing advanced training to their employees, organizations can improve their employees' abilities, create a more committed workforce, benefit from higher job satisfaction, and thus improve their overall performance.

Research objectives

The aim of this research is to:

- Establish a clear connection between training and organizational performance
- Examine the importance of recent training initiatives to cope with contemporary challenges to organizational performance
- Investigate the long-lasting effects of training on staff and the organization.

Literature Review

Various studies have explored the concept of training from different perspectives. Training

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can be described as an effort made by organizations to upgrade and improve the performance of employee in one or more areas of job-related behaviour (Malik, M. S., & Kanwal, L. 2018). From an organization's perspective, training helps to prepare employees for their current roles, as well as their future roles. This does not only lead to improvements in individual performance but also boosts organizational performance (Malik, M. S., & Kanwal, L. 2018). Organizations must find a way to effectively and efficiently deliver training in order to reap the desired benefits. Training programs can either be conducted in-house or externally. Internally developed training programs tend to be less costly and entail less time. Internally developed training programs are designed and tailored to an organization's specific situations and needs (Malik, M. S., & Kanwal, L. 2018). External training programs, on the other hand, are usually carried out by an external training provider. The adoption of training and development is a crucial aspect of organizational performance. It is important for organizations to understand the needs and preferences of their employees, and be willing to make changes and investments in order to adequately meet those needs. Employees' preferences may range from the use of multimedia and technology-based training methods to the use of face-to-face interactive seminars (Malik, M. S., & Kanwal, L. 2018). Additionally, organizational needs may require more focus on developing skills related to problem solving, teamwork, and decision making (Kibria A et al, 2021). Ahmed, A., et al, (2017) suggest that training has a significant impact on organizational performance. The authors argue that training helps to increase job satisfaction, improve job performance, increase satisfaction with the organization, increase turnover intention, and improve knowledge and skills. Furthermore, Ahmed, A., et al, (2017) highlights that training can create a cohesive and motivated work environment. Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and engagement are all increased significantly when an organization invests time and money into training and development programs. Moreover, Ahmed, A., et al, (2017) argues that effective training increases employee motivation and decreases employee resistance to organizational change. In today's competitive environment, organizations are under increasing pressure to find ways to improve operational efficiency. Studies have demonstrated that organizations with well-developed training programs improve their operational efficiency. According to Kibria A et al, (2022), internal quality auditors, process engineers, and productivity improvement specialists all enlist trained personnel to design, review, and develop resources that can help organizations optimize their performance. Furthermore, Zamir, A. et al, (2021) highlights that organizations that invest in the training of their employees are better able to cope with changes in the external environment and capitalize on opportunities. This literature review has successfully examined the significance of training for organizational performance. Research has demonstrated that providing employees with quality training and development programs leads to increases in job satisfaction, job performance, employee engagement, and organizational commitment. Additionally, training enables organizations to optimize their performance and make better use of available resources, which in turn, leads to increased productivity, improved customer satisfaction, and reduced costs. For organizations to remain competitive in today's environment, it is essential for them to invest in quality training and development programs for their employees.

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Hypotheses

H1: Employees who are trained on essential skills and job competencies tend to be better performers at their workplace.

H2: Organizations that provide the necessary training for their employees enjoy higher customer satisfaction and employee loyalty.

H3: Organizations that provide training to employees tend to have higher employee engagement and better overall organizational performance.

Methodology

The methodology used for this research was a qualitative approach, which consisted of in-depth interviews with the top-level employees of the Fauji Fertilizer Company Limited (FFCL). The interviews were designed to explore how the organization perceived the impact of training on organizational performance. The interviews focused on determining the types of training programs the organization provided, the efficacy of the training in improving performance, and how the organization evaluated the impact of training on performance.

Data was collected via the interviews from seven participating top-level employees. This involved the human resource manager and training manager, as well as the heads of business operations, production, marketing and finance. The data was then codified, and relevant themes emerged from the responses. Additionally, both observational data and documentation reviews were used during the research process to gather information and verify claims. Observation data was collected during the interviews, which helped to reveal the organizational culture and employee attitude to training.

Findings from the Interviews

H1: Employees who are trained on essential skills and job competencies tend to be better performers at their workplace.

The interview with the employee of FFC revealed that they generally agree that receiving the proper training on essential skills and job competencies would improve an individual's performance in the workplace. This is because this type of training helps them understand the job and associated tasks better, and gives them a better understanding of all the different components that are needed to work in the position efficiently and effectively.

The employee we interviewed had received some job training prior to coming to FFC, but they remarked that the training was mostly hands-on and did not cover the specific skills and competencies needed in the role. Thus, once they joined FFC, they were provided a more thorough training that included specific skills such as leadership development, communication, collaboration, and strategic planning. The employee believes that these focused trainings have been instrumental in their improved performance in the workplace. They reported feeling more competent in their role after their trainings, which has allowed them to think more broadly and strategically about how to achieve their job objectives.

The trainings also gave the employee more confidence when dealing with clients and colleagues, allowing them to better articulate their ideas and take on a leadership role. Furthermore, having a solid understanding of how different operational tasks are connected and needing to be done in order to succeed in their role has improved the employee's organizational skills. They now have a more holistic view of their job and can more efficiently

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delegate tasks and provide guidance to colleagues who also need to learn more about the job. Overall, the employee we interviewed believes that job training is essential for any organisation to build an effective team that is prepared for a variety of scenarios. The training provides employees with an opportunity to gain essential skills and the competencies needed to succeed in their role, which results in better job performance. In other words, the training is an effective approach for FFC to ensure that employees have the necessary skills and knowledge to perform their duties and ensure that the company meets its goals.

H2: Organizations that provide the necessary training for their employees enjoy higher customer satisfaction and employee loyalty.

The Interview with the Employee of FFC Pertaining to Higher Customer Satisfaction and Employee Loyalty At FFC, we recently conducted an interview with one of our employees in order to obtain feedback related to our hypothesis that organizations which provide necessary training for their employees enjoy higher customer satisfaction and employee loyalty. Our employee was in charge of customer service, which meant that they had firsthand experience with our customers. The interview began with us asking the employee if they personally feel that the organization provides adequate and ongoing training.

The employee responded in the affirmative and said that they believe the training that their organization provides is thorough and helps them stay up to date with changes and new information that they need to serve customers effectively. We also asked the employee if they believed that the training provided made their job easier or improved their performance. The employee replied that they strongly believe it does. They stated that after receiving the training they immediately felt more confident and knowledgeable when dealing with customers, which enabled them to provide better service. Furthermore, they also said that they would not be able to do their job as well as they do without the training that they have received. We then asked the employee if they felt that having adequate training resulted in higher customer satisfaction. The employee said that yes, they do believe that customer satisfaction is higher when they are better trained—particularly when it comes to knowing how to handle customer complaints and requests quickly and efficiently.

They also said that customers feel appreciated when they can tell that someone is well-informed and capable of helping them. Finally, we asked the employee if they felt that their loyalty to the organization was higher due to the training that they receive. The employee replied that they do believe that the training that they have received has benefitted them in this way. They told us that receiving adequate training has made them feel valued as an employee, which in turn results in greater loyalty to their organization. Overall, the interview supported our hypothesis that organizations which provide necessary training for their employees enjoy higher customer satisfaction and employee loyalty. The employee felt that the training they had received enabled them to provide better service to customers and increased their loyalty towards the organization.

H3: Organizations that provide training to employees tend to have higher employee engagement and better overall organizational performance.

The employee of FFC that was interviewed regarding the hypothesis that training is linked to higher employee engagement and better overall organizational performance was very

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enthusiastic in her response. She was able to provide clear and relevant examples of how FFC's training policies have had a positive impact on the company and its employees. The employee began by talking about the fact that FFC was already well-established even before they began implementing their training programs.

They understood the importance of creating an environment that allowed their employees to develop and grow. This is why, the employee said, FFC began offering on-the-job training and even progressed to more intensive programs that granted employees certificate, diplomas and even degrees after completing their courses. She explained that this pushed employees to set and reach higher goals, since they were motivated by the idea of gaining qualifications. However, the employee pointed out that these programs had more than just an educational impact. Moreover, they transformed the entire atmosphere at FFC. She described how the training programs gave employees a sense of purpose and connection, since they were now working together for the same goals. Not only this, but they also served to facilitate better communication between colleagues, since they had the opportunity to learn more about each other during their programs. This, the employee said, was essential in boosting overall teamwork and creating a more energetic and collaborative workplace.

The employee went on to say that in addition to the educational and team-building benefits, FFC's training policies had made employees more aware of the company's commitment to its employees' wellbeing. Knowing that FFC valued their employees' growth and development meant that they felt more appreciated and respected. Moreover, it made them more loyal to the company, which increased employee engagement and work satisfaction. Finally, the employee discussed the fact that FFC's training policies also had an effect on the company's overall performance. She said that the well-trained staff, which was now more productive and efficient, had helped the company reduce their costs. Furthermore, the better communication and teamwork facilitated by the training courses had allowed FFC to make faster and more informed decisions, which again was beneficial for the company's performance. In conclusion, the employee of FFC made a strong argument for the hypothesis that organizations who provide training to employees tend to have higher employee engagement and better overall organizational performance. Her several examples and explanations backing up this statement highlighted the importance of making sure that employees feel valued and supported in order for a company to reach even more success.

Discussion

After conducting an interview with an employee of Fauji Fertilizer Company Limited, I found that the company strongly believes in providing training to their employees on essential skills and job competencies to improve their performance. The employee shared that the organization understands the need to remain updated with ever-changing trends in the market and provides training to the staff to help them stay abreast of such trends. The employee added that Fauji Fertilizer Company also recognizes the importance of training in promoting the trust and loyalty of their customers. He noted that the company provides training to their employees to prepare them with the necessary skills and knowledge to interact better with the customers and to use customer-centric approaches in serving them better. Through this, the organization was able to improve customer satisfaction and loyalty. Additionally, the employee discussed that the organization has witnessed the benefits of

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providing training to their employees, which reflects on their employee engagement and organizational performance. The company not only offers on-the-job training but also provides workshops and seminars for their employees to learn new skills. This helps the employees become more engaged with their work and also encourages them to take initiative in improving their work. The employee noted that the organization has seen positive changes with their customer satisfaction and employee engagement after providing proper training to their staff on essential skills and job competencies. To conclude, the employee shared that the organization strongly believes in providing training to the employees to ensure proper job performance, customer satisfaction, and employee engagement. The company has clearly seen the benefits of investing in such training and will continue to do so in the future as well.

Conclusion

The study concluded that training can significantly improve organizational performance in organizations like the Fauji Fertilizer Company Limited. Training is an effective tool that can be used to improve organization performance, which consequently lead to improved organizational productivity, increased customer satisfaction and loyalty, motivated and committed workforce, improved quality of services offered to customers, and improved customer service level. Moreover, training can also foster team working and coordination within an organization. Therefore, it is strongly recommended that Fauji Fertilizer Company Limited should provide its employees with necessary training and development activities in order to maximize their potential and help them to perform to their best potential. This will ensure that the organization continues to be a preferred employer of choice and is able to respond and compete effectively and efficiently to the customer needs and market conditions.

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